

General_WU_no20_publiclink_May9

Start of Block: consent block

Q1 Click to write the question text

Browser (1)

Version (2)

Operating System (3)

Screen Resolution (4)

Flash Version (5)

Java Support (6)

User Agent (7)

Q2 **Welcome! Thank you for your help with this hunting research.** This questionnaire is part of a research study being conducted by the Department of Environmental Studies and Sciences at **Santa Clara University**. This survey concerns opinions about hunting and habitat quality, and is only open to adult (18+) hunters who hunt in Northern California.

Your participation, if you choose to fill out the survey, will take about **15 minutes**. Your participation is **voluntary**. You don't have to take the survey, and if you change your mind, you can quit the survey whenever you want.

This survey is confidential and we don't require you to give us any personally identifiable information. If the results are published in the future, no information that can identify you as a participant will be released.

The faculty advisor for this research is Dr. Virginia Matzek in the SCU Department of Environmental Studies and Sciences. If you have any questions concerning the conduct of the study, feel free to email Dr. Matzek at vmatzek@scu.edu. If you have any questions about your rights as a subject/participant in this research, or if you feel you have been placed at risk, you can contact the Chair of the Human Subjects Committee through the Office of Research Compliance and Integrity at 408-554-5591. **By clicking the "Advance survey" button below, you are consenting to participate. Thank you for helping us with this project.**

Advance survey (1)

Quit and end survey now (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Welcome! Thank you for your help with this hunting research. This questionnaire is part of a... = Quit and end survey now

End of Block: consent block

Start of Block: Intercept follow up

Q3 Did you hunt on public lands in Northern California in the last 2 years?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Skip To: End of Survey If Did you hunt on public lands in Northern California in the last 2 years? = No

Q4

Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years

Which of these game species have you hunted on public lands in Northern California in the past 2 years?

(please check all that apply)

- Turkey (1)
- Pheasant (2)
- Other Upland Gamebirds (besides Turkey or Pheasant) (3)
- Waterfowl (4)
- Deer (5)
- Other big game (Bear, Elk, Bighorn Sheep, Pronghorn Antelope, or Wild Pig) (6)
- Did not hunt public lands in N. California in the last two years (7)

End of Block: Intercept follow up

Start of Block: Harvest

Display This Question:

If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Other Upland Gamebirds (besides Turkey or Pheasant)

Or Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Pheasant

Or Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Turkey

Or Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Waterfowl

Q5 Harvest of \${e://Field/Bird_fill}

Did you get your daily bag limit of \${e://Field/Bird_fill} anywhere in Northern California on any day in the last 2 years?

Display This Choice:
If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Turkey

Display This Choice:
If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Pheasant

Display This Choice:
If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Other Upland Gamebirds (besides Turkey or Pheasant)

Display This Choice:
If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Waterfowl

	Yes (1)	No (2)
<p><i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Turkey</i></p> <p>Turkey (Q61_1)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p><i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Pheasant</i></p> <p>Pheasant (Q61_2)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p><i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have yo... = Other Upland Gamebirds (besides Turkey or Pheasant)</i></p> <p>Other Upland Gamebirds (not Turkey or Pheasant) (Q61_3)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p><i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Your Hunting in Northern</i></p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

California during the last 2
Years Which of these game
species have yo... = Waterfowl

Waterfowl (Q86_4)

Display This Question:

If Your Hunting in Northern California during the last 2 Years Which of these game species have
yo... = Deer

X→

Q6 Harvest of deer

Did you harvest a deer anywhere in Northern California in the past 2 years?

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: Harvest

Start of Block: Satisfaction

Q7

$\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting

The following questions are about $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ hunting.

X→

Q8 $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Satisfaction

Thinking about the places you hunted $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ in Northern California in the past 2 years, please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements about your hunting satisfaction.

	Disagree (1)	Somewhat Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat Agree (4)	Agree (5)
my overall hunting experience (Q7_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
my harvest (Q7_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
number of shots I could take (Q7_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
amount of game I saw (Q7_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
habitat quality (Q7_5)	<input type="radio"/>				
area available for hunting (Q7_6)	<input type="radio"/>				
level of crowding near hunting spots (Q7_7)	<input type="radio"/>				
ease of access to hunting areas (Q7_8)	<input type="radio"/>				
etiquette of other hunters (Q7_9)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q9

Trends in your satisfaction

In recent years hunting [\\${e://Field/Species_CE}](#) in Northern California, has your satisfaction with each of the following decreased, stayed the same, or increased?

	My satisfaction has Decreased (1)	My satisfaction has Stayed the same (2)	My satisfaction has Increased (3)
my overall hunting experience (Q8_1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
my harvest (Q8_2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
number of shots I could take (Q8_3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
amount of game I saw (Q8_4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
habitat quality (Q8_5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
area available for hunting (Q8_6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
level of crowding near hunting spots (Q8_7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 ease of access to hunting areas (Q8_8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
 etiquette of other hunters (Q8_9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

End of Block: Satisfaction

Start of Block: Trip reporting-waterfowl

Q10 Your Waterfowl Hunting Areas

The following map shows several waterfowl hunting areas in Northern California.

1. In the past 2 years, did you hunt waterfowl in any of these areas?

	Yes (1)	No (2)
1. Upper Butte Basin Wildlife Area (Q9_1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Gray Lodge Wildlife Area (Q9_2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Fremont Weir Wildlife Area (Q9_3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Yolo Basin Wildlife Area (Q9_4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Grizzly Island Wildlife Area (Q9_5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. North Bay (Q9_6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. South Bay (Q9_7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Your Waterfowl Hunting Areas The following map shows several waterfowl hunting areas in Northern... = 6. North Bay [Yes]

Q11 North Bay Waterfowl Areas

Below is a map of waterfowl hunting areas within the North Bay area that indicates some areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted waterfowl in the North Bay region, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Your Waterfowl Hunting Areas The following map shows several waterfowl hunting areas in Northern... = 7. South Bay [Yes]

Q12 South Bay Waterfowl Areas

Below is a map of waterfowl hunting areas within the South Bay area that indicates areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted waterfowl in the South Bay region, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: Trip reporting-waterfowl

Start of Block: CE1 Intro waterfowl

Q13 Waterfowl Hunting Sites

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about factors that may affect the places where you choose to hunt waterfowl:

	Disagree (1)	Somewhat Disagree (2)	Neither (3)	Somewhat Agree (4)	Agree (5)
I am unwilling to travel over 90 miles to reach a hunting site (Q12_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
I usually hunt at sites with more open clearings than dense vegetation (Q12_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
I will not hunt at sites I can't access by motorboat (Q12_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
I base my choice of where to hunt mainly on my chances of success at the site (Q12_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
I only hunt at sites where other hunters are unlikely to affect my shots (Q12_5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q14 Your Preferences Toward Different Waterfowl Hunting Sites

This section asks about your preferences for hunting sites that differ in their attributes. We will present five scenarios, each asking you to consider a trip to two possible hunting sites. For each scenario, we would like you to consider which site you would prefer to visit, including the possibility of taking no trip at all.

The alternative hunting sites will vary in several attributes, such as hunting success, habitat, and the round trip time it takes to drive to each site.

Q15

Wetland habitat types

In some of the upcoming questions, you will be asked to distinguish among **wetland habitat types**, including "open water," "sparse vegetation," and "dense vegetation." These are marshes, bays, ponds, lakes, rivers, or sloughs that differ chiefly in how thickly vegetated they are.

Open Water

Open water habitats have large expanses of open water, with vegetation confined to the fringes. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Sparse Vegetation

Sparse vegetation habitats have small islands of vegetation amid expanses of open water. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Dense Vegetation

Dense vegetation habitats have large expanses of thick vegetation, with open water occurring only as narrow channels or small openings. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Q16

Although there is variation in each of the three habitat types, we will use the following pictures to represent the three wetland habitats:

Which of the three habitat types best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most waterfowl hunting the last 2 years?

- Open Water (1)
- Sparse Vegetation (2)
- Dense Vegetation (3)

Page Break _____

Q17 Hunting Success

In the next part of the survey, we will refer to "**Hunting Success**" as follows: Waterfowl hunting success means you harvest your **daily bag limit**.

Not all hunting trips are successful by this definition. So if we say a site has a "50% chance of success," it will mean that on any visit there is a 50% chance you will get your daily bag limit when you hunt waterfowl.

Which of these chances of hunting success best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most waterfowl hunting in the last 2 years?

- 90%** chance of hunting success (1)
- 70%** chance of hunting success (2)
- 50%** chance of hunting success (3)
- 30%** chance of hunting success (4)
- 10%** chance of hunting success (5)

Page Break

Q18 Effect Crowding has on Your Hunting

Crowding at hunting sites can affect how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot. In this survey we will refer to the effect that crowding can have on your hunting using these three levels: **Rarely**: Rarely affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot
Sometimes: Sometimes affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot
Often: Often affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot

Which of the following best describes how crowding affected your hunting the last 2 years?

- Rarely (1)
 - Sometimes (2)
 - Often (3)
-

Q19 Water Levels at Hunting Sites

Water levels at some hunting sites fluctuate **naturally** depending on weather and hydrology. For example, areas connected to the ocean may fluctuate depending on tides. Alternatively, water levels at some sites may be **managed** with levees, pumps, or other control mechanisms.

In this survey, we refer to two types of water levels at hunting sites: **Natural**: Varies depending on weather and hydrology **Managed**: Controlled by structures and levels are adjusted by site managers

Which best describes water levels at the site where you did the most waterfowl hunting the last 2 years?

- Natural (1)
- Managed (2)

End of Block: CE1 Intro waterfowl

Start of Block: Trip reporting-upland

Q20 Your $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Areas

The following map shows several $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ hunting areas in Northern California.

1. In the past 2 years, did you hunt $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ at any of these areas?

	Yes (1)	No (2)
1. Sacramento River Area 1 (Q122_1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Sacramento River Area 2 (Q122_2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Sacramento River Area 3 (Q122_3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Upper Butte Wildlife Area (Q122_4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Oroville Wildlife Area (Q122_5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Gray Lodge Wildlife Area (Q122_6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Feather River Wildlife Area (Q122_7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. Fremont Weir Wildlife Area (Q122_8)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Your $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Areas The following map shows several ... = 1.
Sacramento River Area 1 [Yes]

Q21 Sacramento River Area 1

Below is a map of hunting areas within Sacramento River Area 1 that indicates some areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted in Sacramento River Area 1 for $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Display This Question:

If Your $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Areas The following map shows several ... = 2.
Sacramento River Area 2 [Yes]

Q22 Sacramento River Area 2

Below is a map of hunting areas within Sacramento River Area 2 that indicates some areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted in Sacramento River Area 2 for $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Display This Question:

If Your $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Areas The following map shows several ... = 3.
Sacramento River Area 3 [Yes]

Q23 Sacramento River Area 3

Below is a map of hunting areas within Sacramento River Area 3 that indicates some areas shaded in **green**.

2. In the past 2 years, when you hunted in Sacramento River Area 3 for $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$, did you go to any of the **green** areas of the map?

Yes (1)

No (2)

End of Block: Trip reporting-upland

Start of Block: CE1 Intro upland

Q24 $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about factors that may affect the places where you choose to hunt $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$?

	Disagree (1)	Somewhat disagree (2)	Neither (3)	Somewhat agree (4)	Agree (5)
I am unwilling to travel over 90 miles to reach a hunting site (Q14_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
I usually hunt at sites with more open clearings than dense vegetation (Q14_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
I will not hunt at sites where I can't bring dogs (Q14_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
I base my choice of where to hunt mainly on my chances of success at the site (Q14_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
I only hunt at sites where other hunters are unlikely to affect my shots (Q14_5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q25 Your Preferences Toward Different $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites

This section asks about your preferences for hunting sites that differ in their attributes. We will present five scenarios, each asking you to consider a trip to two possible hunting sites. For each scenario, we would like you to consider which site you would prefer to visit, including the possibility of taking no trip at all.

The alternative hunting sites will vary in several attributes, such as hunting success, habitat, and the round trip time it takes to drive to each site.

Q26

Upland habitat types

In some of the upcoming questions, you will be asked to distinguish among **upland habitat types**, including "grassland," "open woodland," and "forest." These are dry, upland areas that differ chiefly in how densely wooded with shrubs and trees they are.

Grassland Grassland habitats have large expanses of grasses, flowers, and weeds with an occasional tree or shrub. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Open woodland Open woodland habitats are sparsely wooded, with a patchy distribution of young trees and shrubs. Here are some pictures of this habitat type:

Forests Forest habitats are densely wooded, with a continuous canopy of tall trees overhead. Here are some pictures of this habitat type:

Q27

Although there is variation in each of the three habitat types, in the rest of this survey we will use the following pictures to represent the three upland habitats:

Which of the three habitat types best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most [\\${e://Field/Species_CE}](#) hunting the last 2 years?

- Grassland (1)
- Open Woodland (2)
- Forest (3)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Species_CE = turkey

Q28 Hunting Success

In the next part of the survey, we will refer to "**Hunting Success**" as follows: Turkey hunting success means you harvest your **daily bag limit**.

Not all hunting trips are successful by this definition. So if we say a site has a "50% chance of success," it will mean that on any visit there is a 50% chance you will get your daily bag limit when you hunt turkey.

Which of these chances of hunting success best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ hunting in the last 2 years?

- 90% chance of hunting success (1)
- 70% chance of hunting success (2)
- 50% chance of hunting success (3)
- 30% chance of hunting success (4)
- 10% chance of hunting success (5)

Display This Question:

If Species_CE = deer

Q29 Hunting Success

In the next part of the survey, we will refer to "**Hunting Success**" as follows: Deer hunting success means you fill a deer tag.

Not all hunting trips are successful by this definition. So if we say a site has a "50% chance of success," it will mean that on any visit there is a 50% chance you will fill a deer tag when you hunt deer.

Which of these chances of hunting success best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most `Species_CE` hunting in the last 2 years?

- 90%** chance of hunting success (1)
- 70%** chance of hunting success (2)
- 50%** chance of hunting success (3)
- 30%** chance of hunting success (4)
- 10%** chance of hunting success (5)

Display This Question:

If Species_CE = pheasant

Or Species_CE = upland gamebirds

Q30 Hunting Success

In the next part of the survey, we will refer to "**Hunting Success**" as follows: Upland Gamebirds hunting success means you harvest your **daily bag limit**.

Not all hunting trips are successful by this definition. So if we say a site has a "50% chance of success," it will mean that on any visit there is a 50% chance you will get your daily bag limit when you hunt upland gamebirds.

Which of these chances of hunting success best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most `Field/Species_CE` hunting in the last 2 years?

- 90% chance of hunting success (1)
 - 70% chance of hunting success (2)
 - 50% chance of hunting success (3)
 - 30% chance of hunting success (4)
 - 10% chance of hunting success (5)
-

Q31 Effect Crowding has on Your Hunting

Crowding at hunting sites can affect how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot. In this survey we will refer to the effect that crowding can have on your hunting using these three levels:

Rarely: Rarely affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot

Sometimes: Sometimes affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot

Often: Often affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot

Which of the following best describes how crowding affected your hunting the last 2 years?

- Rarely (1)
 - Sometimes (2)
 - Often (3)
-

Q32 Dogs at Hunting Sites

Some hunting sites allow dogs and others do not.

Are dogs allowed at the site you did the most $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ hunting in the last 2 years?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

End of Block: CE1 Intro upland

Start of Block: Choice Experiment CE1

Q33

Note: If you are using a mobile device, the following questions are best viewed by turning the device sideways (widescreen).

Q34

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites

Consider the two sites in each table below. Each site has different levels of site attributes like driving distance and habitat. ($\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Click here for a reminder of what these attribute levels mean.)

Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 1

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site A

Site B

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_A1\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_B1\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_B1\}$

$\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_A1\}$

Chance of

hunting success	$\{e://Field/Success_A1\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_B1\}$	Huntable area
$\{e://Field/Area_A1\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Area_B1\}$ acres		Crowding affects shots
$\{e://Field/Crowding_A1\}$	$\{e://Field/Crowding_B1\}$		Round trip driving time
$\{e://Field/Time_A1\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Time_B1\}$ minutes		

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Q35 1. Based on the hunting site attributes in the table above, which site would you hunt at?

- I would hunt Site A (1)
- I would hunt Site B (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If 1. Based on the hunting site attributes in the table above, which site would you hunt at? = I would not go hunting

Q36

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site A is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site B is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If 1. Based on the hunting site attributes in the table above, which site would you hunt at? = I would hunt Site B

Q37

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site A is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If 1. Based on the hunting site attributes in the table above, which site would you hunt at? = I would hunt Site A

Q38

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site B is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Page Break

Q39

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 5)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 2

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site C

Site D

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_A2\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_B2\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_A2\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_B2\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_A2\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_B2\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_A2\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_B2\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_A2\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_B2\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_A2\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_B2\}$ minutes

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1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site C (1)
- I would hunt Site D (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 5) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q40 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site C is my least favorite (1)
- Site D is my least favorite (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site C

Q41 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site D is my least favorite (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site D

Q42 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site C is my least favorite (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Page Break

Q43

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 5)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 3

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site F

Site G

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_A3\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_B3\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_A3\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_B3\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_A3\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_B3\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_A3\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_B3\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_A3\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_B3\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_A3\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_B3\}$ minutes

	Site F	Site G
Habitat type	$\{e://Field/Habitat_A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Habitat_B3\}$
Water Dog	$\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$	$\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$
Dogs	$\{e://Field/Dogs_A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Dogs_B3\}$
Chance of hunting success	$\{e://Field/Success_A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_B3\}$
Huntability	$\{e://Field/Success_A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_B3\}$
Huntable area	$\{e://Field/Area_A3\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Area_B3\}$ acres
Crowding affects shots	$\{e://Field/Crowding_A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Crowding_B3\}$
Round trip driving time	$\{e://Field/Time_A3\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Time_B3\}$ minutes

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site F (1)
- I would hunt Site G (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 5) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q44

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site F is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site G is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site G

Q45

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site F is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site F

Q46

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site G is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Q47

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 4 of 5)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 4

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site H

Site I

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_A4\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_B4\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_A4\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_B4\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_A4\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_B4\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_A4\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_B4\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_A4\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_B4\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_A4\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_B4\}$ minutes

$\{e://Field/Time_A4\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Time_B4\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Success_A4\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_B4\}$	$\{e://Field/Area_A4\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Area_B4\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Crowding_A4\}$	$\{e://Field/Crowding_B4\}$	$\{e://Field/Dogs_A4\}$	$\{e://Field/Dogs_B4\}$	$\{e://Field/Habitat_A4\}$	$\{e://Field/Habitat_B4\}$

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site H (1)
- I would hunt Site I (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 4 of 5) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q48

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site H is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site I is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 4 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site I

Q49

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site H is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 4 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site H

Q50

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site I is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Q51

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 5 of 5)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 5

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE1\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site J

Site K

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_A5\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_B5\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_A5\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_B5\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_A5\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_B5\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_A5\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_B5\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_A5\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_B5\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_A5\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_B5\}$ minutes

$\{e://Field/Time_A5\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Time_B5\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Success_A5\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_B5\}$	$\{e://Field/Area_A5\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Area_B5\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Habitat_A5\}$	$\{e://Field/Habitat_B5\}$	$\{e://Field/Water_Dog\}$	$\{e://Field/Dogs_A5\}$	$\{e://Field/Dogs_B5\}$

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site J (1)
- I would hunt Site K (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 5 of 5) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q52

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site J is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site K is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 5 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site K

Q53

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site J is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 5 of 5) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site J

Q54

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site K is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Start of Block: Demographics

Q55 Summaries of our final questions help us represent the activities of a range of hunters. Individual answers remain strictly confidential.

Q56 How many years old are you?

- 18 - 24 (1)
 - 25 - 34 (2)
 - 35 - 44 (3)
 - 45 - 54 (4)
 - 55 - 64 (5)
 - 65 - 74 (6)
 - 75 - 84 (7)
 - 85 or over (8)
-

Q57 How many years have you been hunting?

Q58 What is your sex?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
-

Q59 What is the highest level or grade of school you have completed?

- Some high school or less (1)
 - High school graduate or GED (2)
 - Some college, no degree (3)
 - Two-year college (AA, AS) or technical degree (4)
 - Four-year college graduate (BA, BS) (5)
 - Some graduate work but did not receive a graduate degree (6)
 - Graduate degree (MA, MBA, PhD, JD, etc.) (7)
-

Q60 What is the zip code for the location where you lived during the 2019-20 hunting season (prior to the pandemic)?

- Zip code (19) _____
-

Q61 What best describes your employment status during the 2019-20 hunting season (prior to the pandemic)?

- Employed full time (1)
 - Employed part time (2)
 - Unemployed looking for work (3)
 - Unemployed not looking for work (4)
 - Retired (5)
 - Student (6)
 - Homemaker (7)
 - Unable to work (8)
-

Q62 How many children younger than 18 lived in your household during the 2019-20 hunting season (prior to the pandemic)?

- None (0)
 - 1 (1)
 - 2 (2)
 - 3 (3)
 - 4 (4)
 - 5 or more (5)
-

Q63 Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in your household during the 2019-20 hunting season (prior to the pandemic)?

- Less than \$25,000 per year (1)
- \$25,000 to \$49,999 per year (2)
- \$50,000 to \$74,999 per year (3)
- \$75,000 to \$99,999 (4)
- \$100,000 to \$149,999 (5)
- \$150,000 to \$199,999 (6)
- Over \$200,000 (7)

Display This Question:

*If Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
Less than \$25,000 per year*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
\$25,000 to \$49,999 per year*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
\$50,000 to \$74,999 per year*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
\$75,000 to \$99,999*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
\$100,000 to \$149,999*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
\$150,000 to \$199,999*

*And Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in y... !=
Over \$200,000*

Q64 Summary data on hunter incomes is an important part of representing the views of area hunters. The information is strictly confidential and is not linked to your name. Which of the following best describes the total income before taxes of all the people living in your household during the 2019-20 hunting season (prior to the pandemic)?

- Less than \$75,000 (1)
- \$75,000 or more (2)

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Additional hunting Q's

Q65

`{e://Field/Species_CE_Cap}` Hunting in Northern California

Q66 Do you hunt `{e://Field/Species_CE}` in Northern California less than often than desired?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q67 In your opinion, how much effect, if any, do the following factors have on how often you hunt $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ in Northern California?

	No effect (1)	Weak effect (2)	Moderate effect (3)	Strong effect (4)	Extremely strong effect (5)
Your work obligations (Q50_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Your family obligations (Q50_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of mobility impaired access (Q50_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Your health (Q50_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Cost (Q50_5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Reservation availability at best hunt areas (Q50_6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Length or timing of season (Q50_7)	<input type="radio"/>				
Bag limits (Q50_8)	<input type="radio"/>				
Lead shot ban (Q50_9)	<input type="radio"/>				
Etiquette of other hunters (Q50_10)	<input type="radio"/>				
Lack of hunting partners (Q50_11)	<input type="radio"/>				

Lack of hunting access (Q50_12)

Low wildlife populations (Q50_13)

Other: (Q50_14)

Q68 In your opinion, how much effect, if any, do the following factors have on population sizes of $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ in areas you hunt in Northern California?

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE = waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE != waterfowl

	No effect (1)	Weak effect (2)	Moderate effect (3)	Strong effect (4)	Extremely strong effect (5)
Natural predators (Q51_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
Hunting pressure (Q51_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Poaching (Q51_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Drought (Q51_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Wildfire (Q51_5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Invasive species (Q51_6)	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Species_CE = waterfowl</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
Wind turbines (Q51_7)	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Species_CE != waterfowl</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
Urban/suburban sprawl (Q51_8)	<input type="radio"/>				

Other: (Q51_9)

Q69 How concerned are you about the following issues affecting your $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ hunting, now or in the future?

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE = waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE != waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE = waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE = waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE != waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Specie_CE = waterfowl

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE != waterfowl

	Not at all concerned (1)	Slightly concerned (2)	Moderately concerned (3)	Very concerned (4)	Extremely concerned (5)
Invasive species (Q52_1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Species_CE = waterfowl</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sea level rise (Q52_2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Species_CE != waterfowl</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Climate change (Q52_3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If</i>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Species_CE = waterfowl

Levee failure
(Q52_4)

Drought
(Q52_5)

Wildfire
(Q52_6)

Poaching
(Q52_7)

Display This Choice:

If Species_CE = waterfowl

Wind turbines
(Q52_8)

Display This Choice:

If Species_CE != waterfowl

Urban/suburban
sprawl (Q52_9)

Rise in
license/tag fees
(Q52_10)

Display This Choice:

If Specie_CE = waterfowl

Rise in site fees
(e.g., boat
launch parking,
lands pass,
daily access
permits)
(Q52_11)

Display This Choice:

If
Species_CE !=
waterfowl

Rise in site fees
(e.g., parking,
lands pass,
daily access
permits)
(Q52_12)

Decline in
hunting by
young people
(Q52_13)

New restrictions
on access to
guns or ammo
(Q52_14)

New restrictions
on hunting
access, or
closure of hunt
areas (Q52_15)

Hunting
pressure
(Q52_16)

Natural
predators
(Q52_17)

<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="radio"/>				

Page Break

Q70 For the next 3 questions, suppose that a $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ parcel near your favorite hunting spot for $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ is being restored to improve habitat quality. The restored habitat has potential to increase $\{e://Field/Species_CE\}$ populations at the site where you hunt now, and it would also be a good spot for hunting.

1. Which of these two options would you prefer?

- The $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ would be open to hunting so that I have more places to harvest game. (1)
 - The $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ would be closed to hunting so that game populations can increase near my favorite spot. (2)
-

Q71 2. If the $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ were opened to hunting, which would you prefer?

- The $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ would be only open to private hunting, such as paying members of a club. (1)
 - The $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ would be open to all public hunters, under state or federal hunt regulations. (2)
-

Q72 3. If the $\{e://Field/Parcel\}$ were opened to public hunting, which would you prefer?

- The habitat would be managed by California Department of Fish and Wildlife. (1)
- The habitat would be managed by US Fish and Wildlife. (2)

End of Block: Additional hunting Q's

Start of Block: Corona Q's

Q73

Coronavirus and your hunting

Please indicate your agreement or disagreement with the following statements about how the COVID-19 pandemic affected your hunting this season.

Display This Choice:
If Species_CE = waterfowl

	Disagree (1)	Somewhat Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Somewhat Agree (4)	Agree (5)
I hunted less frequently than in past years (Q56_1)	<input type="radio"/>				
I tended to hunt alone, or with fewer companions, compared to the past (Q56_2)	<input type="radio"/>				
More than in the past, I tended to avoid sites with check-in stations (Q56_3)	<input type="radio"/>				
I changed what days I hunted, or what sites I visited, in order to avoid crowds (Q56_4)	<input type="radio"/>				
<i>Display This Choice:</i> <i>If Species_CE = waterfowl</i>	<input type="radio"/>				
I avoided sites with lottery entry or sweat lines (Q56_5)	<input type="radio"/>				

Start of Block: Other hunters & upland invite

Q74

Other Hunters

Do you know any other Northern California hunters that might be interested in expressing their opinions on these issues?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

*If Other Hunters Do you know any other Northern California hunters that might be interested in
expre... = Yes*

Q75 Please provide an **e-mail address** for other hunters who might be interested in helping us with this research.

Reminder: All information is strictly confidential. We will only use the e-mails to invite hunters to the survey, and we will never use this information for any other purpose.

(Please separate any e-mails with a space or semicolon, or add them to a new line)

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Species_CE2 != skip

Q76 You have completed the main survey!

Before we go to the final question, would you be willing to answer a few questions about [\\${e://Field/Species_CE2}](#) hunting?

- No, take me to the end (1)
- Yes, I'll answer them now (2)
- Yes, but send me a link and I'll do it later (3)

Display This Question:

If You have completed the main survey! Before we go to the final question, would you be willing to a... = Yes, but send me a link and I'll do it later

Q76-3 Please provide an e-mail address for the questions about [\\${e://Field/Species_CE2}](#) hunting?

(Your e-mail will **only** be used to send you a link to the [\\${e://Field/Species_CE2}](#) questions)

- e-mail: (1) _____

End of Block: Other hunters & upland invite

Start of Block: CE2 Intro waterfowl

Q77

[\\${e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap}](#) Hunting

The final section of the survey is about [\\${e://Field/Species_CE2}](#) hunting.

Q78

Wetland habitat types

In some of the upcoming questions, you will be asked to distinguish among **wetland habitat types**, including "open water," "sparse vegetation," and "dense vegetation." These are marshes, bays, ponds, lakes, rivers, or sloughs that differ chiefly in how thickly vegetated they are.

Open Water

Open water habitats have large expanses of open water, with vegetation confined to the fringes. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Sparse Vegetation

Sparse vegetation habitats have small islands of vegetation amid expanses of open water. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Dense Vegetation

Dense vegetation habitats have large expanses of thick vegetation, with open water occurring only as narrow channels or small openings. Here are some pictures of what this habitat type looks like:

Q79

Although there is variation in each of the three habitat types, we will use the following pictures to represent the three wetland habitats:

Which of the three habitat types best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most waterfowl hunting the last 2 years?

- Open Water (1)
- Sparse Vegetation (2)
- Dense Vegetation (3)

Page Break

Q80 **Hunting Success**

In the next part of the survey, we will refer to "**Hunting Success**" as follows: Waterfowl hunting success means you harvest your **daily bag limit**.

Not all hunting trips are successful by this definition. So if we say a site has a "50% chance of success," it will mean that on any visit there is a 50% chance you will get your daily bag limit when you hunt waterfowl.

Which of these chances of hunting success best describes the area in Northern California where you did the most waterfowl hunting in the last 2 years?

- 90%** chance of hunting success (1)
- 70%** chance of hunting success (2)
- 50%** chance of hunting success (3)
- 30%** chance of hunting success (4)
- 10%** chance of hunting success (5)

Page Break

Q81 Effect Crowding has on Your Hunting

Crowding at hunting sites can affect how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot. In this survey we will refer to the effect that crowding can have on your hunting using these three levels: **Rarely**: Rarely affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot
Sometimes: Sometimes affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot
Often: Often affects how much wildlife you see or your ability to take a shot

Which of the following best describes how crowding affected your hunting the last 2 years?

- Rarely (1)
 - Sometimes (2)
 - Often (3)
-

Q82 Water Levels at Hunting Sites

Water levels at some hunting sites fluctuate **naturally** depending on weather and hydrology. For example, areas connected to the ocean may fluctuate depending on tides. Alternatively, water levels at some sites may be **managed** with levees, pumps, or other control mechanisms.

In this survey, we refer to two types of water levels at hunting sites: **Natural**: Varies depending on weather and hydrology **Managed**: Controlled by structures and levels are adjusted by site managers

Which best describes water levels at the site where you did the most waterfowl hunting the last 2 years?

- Natural (1)
- Managed (2)

End of Block: CE2 Intro waterfowl

Start of Block: CE2

Q83

Note: If you are using a mobile device, turn the device sideways (widescreen) for best viewing.

Q84

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 1 of 3)

Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 1

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE2\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site A

Site B

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3A1\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3B1\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog2\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_3A1\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_3B1\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_3A1\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_3B1\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_3A1\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_3B1\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_3A1\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_3B1\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_3A1\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_3B1\}$ minutes

.tg {border-collapse:collapse;border-spacing:0;} .tg td{font-family:Arial, sans-serif;font-size:14px;padding:10px 13px;border-style:solid;border-width:1px;overflow:hidden;word-break:normal;border-color:black;} .tg th{font-family:Arial, sans-serif;font-size:14px;font-weight:normal;padding:10px 13px;border-style:solid;border-width:1px;overflow:hidden;word-break:normal;border-color:black;} .tg .tg-j4pq{background-color:#efefef;border-color:#000000;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-pvtp{background-color:#efefef;border-color:#009901;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-qhnr{background-color:#ecf4ff;border-color:#000000;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-1qc3{text-decoration:underline;background-color:#ecf4ff;border-color:#000000;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-2jbb{font-weight:bold;background-color:#dae8fc;border-color:#000000;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-s9qx{background-color:#dae8fc;border-color:#009901;text-align:center;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-wkkj{font-weight:bold;background-color:#efefef;border-color:#000000;text-align:left;vertical-align:top} .tg .tg-2caz{background-color:#dae8fc;border-color:#009901;text-align:left;vertical-align:top}

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site A (1)
- I would hunt Site B (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 1 of 3) Assume that these... = I would not go hunting

Q85

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site A is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site B is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 1 of 3) Assume that these... = I would hunt Site B

Q86

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site A is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 1 of 3) Assume that these... = I would hunt Site A

Q87

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site B is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Q88

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 3)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 2

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE2\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site C

Site D

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3A2\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3B2\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog2\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_3A2\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_3B2\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_3A2\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_3B2\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_3A2\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_3B2\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_3A2\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_3B2\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_3A2\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_3B2\}$ minutes

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1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site C (1)
- I would hunt Site D (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 3) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q89 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site C is my least favorite (1)
- Site D is my least favorite (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 3) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site C

Q90 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site D is my least favorite (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 2 of 3) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site D

Q91 2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site C is my least favorite (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Page Break

Q92

Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 3)

Here are two other possible hunting sites. Assume that these are the only two hunting sites available to visit, and choosing neither means that you will stay home and not go hunting.

Scenario 3

$\{e://Field/Attribute_Pic_CE2\}$ id="extLink1" target="_blank">Attribute Site F

Site G

Habitat type

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3A3\}$

$\{e://Field/Habitat_3B3\}$ $\{e://Field/Water_Dog2\}$ $\{e://Field/Dogs_3A3\}$

$\{e://Field/Dogs_3B3\}$ Chance of

hunting success $\{e://Field/Success_3A3\}$ $\{e://Field/Success_3B3\}$ Huntable area

$\{e://Field/Area_3A3\}$ acres $\{e://Field/Area_3B3\}$ acres Crowding affects shots

$\{e://Field/Crowding_3A3\}$ $\{e://Field/Crowding_3B3\}$ Round trip driving time

$\{e://Field/Time_3A3\}$ minutes $\{e://Field/Time_3B3\}$ minutes

	$\{e://Field/Time_3A3\}$ minutes	$\{e://Field/Time_3B3\}$ minutes	
hunting success	$\{e://Field/Success_3A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Success_3B3\}$	Huntable area
$\{e://Field/Area_3A3\}$ acres	$\{e://Field/Area_3B3\}$ acres		Crowding affects shots
$\{e://Field/Crowding_3A3\}$	$\{e://Field/Crowding_3B3\}$		Round trip driving time

1. Which hunting site would you choose to hunt at?

- I would hunt Site F (1)
- I would hunt Site G (2)
- I would not go hunting (3)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 3) Here are two other... = I would not go hunting

Q93

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site F is my least favorite option. (1)
- Site G is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 3) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site G

Q94

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site F is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

Display This Question:

If Choosing Possible $\{e://Field/Species_CE2_Cap\}$ Hunting Sites (Scenario 3 of 3) Here are two other... = I would hunt Site F

Q95

2. Which of the remaining two options is your least favorite?

- Site G is my least favorite option. (1)
- Not hunting is my least favorite option. (2)

End of Block: CE2

Start of Block: End comment & no payment

Q96 Thank you for your help. We are interested in your feedback on this survey. If you have any comments on this survey, please provide them here.

Q99 Thank you for completing the survey!
Click this arrow to
submit answers

End of Block: End comment & no payment
